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Exploring urban stressors: A citizen science approach with primary school pupils

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Children and adolescents at higher grades of primary education have a level of understanding and education which can be effectively employed in fairly complex citizen science (CS) approaches. CS has been shown to be an effective tool in primary school curriculums. In our research, a group of 7th grade primary school pupils in Ljubljana, Slovenia, was engaged in a CS project exploring urban stressors, as part of the H2020 URBANOME project (www.urbanome.eu). They investigated differences in exposure to noise and air pollution by measuring respective parameters on alternative routes from home to school using next-generation sensing and monitoring devices. Provided with guidance on how to explore the question of exposure and health, they were encouraged to propose the tools and methods to conduct the experiments. Two devices that measure air quality, one measuring particulate matter and one measuring NO₂, a smartphone with an external microphone measuring noise, and a smartwatch recording heart rate, activity and location, were provided by the research team. Walking routes included a high-traffic road or alternatively, smaller roads removed from the main road, which have much less traffic. The pupils were presented with the results, which showed that the concentrations of particulate matter and NO₂ are higher near the busy road, as are the noise levels. They correctly identified how their personal choices can affect their exposure to various urban stressors. The CS approach showed that a hands-on experience gives pupils a better understanding of their environment and the importance of determining personal exposure to urban stressors.

ORAL PRESENTATION